

Maximum Induced Subgraph of an Augmented Cube

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Abstract : Let $\max_{\mathcal{G}}(m)$ denote the maximum number of edges in a subgraph of graph G induced by m nodes. The n -dimensional augmented cube, denoted as AQ_n , a variation of the hypercube, possesses some properties superior to those of the hypercube. We study the cases when G is the augmented cube AQ_n .

Keywords : interconnection network, augmented cube, induced subgraph, bisection width

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